

Blue or far-red light supplementation induced pre-hardening in the leaves of the *Rht12* wheat dwarfing line: hormonal changes and freezing tolerance

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Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Spectral composition of light treatments at PPFD $250 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. A: White light (W); B: White light supplemented with Far-Red light (W+FR); C: White light enriched with monochromatic Blue ($\lambda_{\text{max}}=410 \text{ nm}$) light (W+B).

Figure S2. The effect of modified spectral conditions on lipid peroxidation at -6°C minimal temperature in the tall (*rht12*) and dwarf (*Rht12*) wheat leaf segments. The samples were collected to measure MDA content subsequently to the freezing tests implemented after 10 days of light supplementation treatments at 15°C. W: white light (control, white colour), W+B: blue light enrichment (blue colour), W+FR: far-red light enrichment (red colour). Solid bars: *rht12*; striped bars: *Rht12*. Values marked with different letters are significantly different from each other at the level of $p \leq 0.05$ ($n=3$).